

GOOD PRACTICES IN ACADEMIC WRITING*

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21058565

Abstract

The study aims to address the issue of academic writing, from the perspective of raising awareness of its importance and identifying models of good practice. The investigation sought to highlight connections between the self-assessed level of academic writing skills and a better understanding of the writing process, compliance with formal requirements, including those related to writing ethics, and the proper use of bibliographic sources. The sample of subjects consisted of 50 first-year master's students from the humanities and social sciences. The results obtained from the applied opinion questionnaire confirmed the established hypotheses, while also emphasizing the need for students to participate in academic writing courses.

Key words: *Academic writing, Scientific text, Documentation, Plagiarism.*

1. Introduction. The process of writing a scientific study

Writing a scientific study is a laborious process, which involves going through several stages and requires compliance with specific standards and conditions. From the moment it is written until publication, the manuscript must also go through several stages. Gemayel (2016, p. 3883) proposes a three-step approach for producing a scientific paper (figure 1).

Figure 1. The process of writing a scientific paper (adapted from Gemayel, 2016, p. 3883)

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Usually, in order to produce a solid study, the writing process involves several stages and working versions: the planning stage; the establishment of the general framework; the development of multiple drafts leading to the final version submitted for publication (Andrei, Chivu, Ioan-Franc, Sima, 2020).

In general, the structure of a scientific article/ study is as follows (adapted from Petrișor, 2015, p. 6): Title; Authors, affiliation, corresponding author; Abstract; Keywords; Introduction; Materials and methods; Results; Discussion; Conclusions; Acknowledgements; Bibliography; Appendices.

2. Requirements for writing a scientific text

How is the text constructed? Below, in Table 1, we present the stages involved in the process of writing a scientific text, as well as the specific requirements of each stage/ section of the study structure.

Table 1. The process of writing a scientific text (Chelcea, 2007; Ilie Rad, 2008, apud Mogonea, Mogonea, Popescu, Ștefan, 2012; Day, Gastel, 2012; Repanovici, 2019, p. 39; Petrișor, 2015)

No.	Sections	Requirements, standards	Suggestions, useful advice
1	Title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Contains the minimum number of words necessary to describe the content of the paper as clearly and accurately as possible - The title may be followed by a subtitle. The title and subtitle must be clearly delimited, for example by a colon (:), with the subtitle containing only complementary information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Formulate short and engaging titles! (they are cited more frequently) -Avoid using abbreviations, acronyms, codes and formulas, especially when they are not commonly used in titles
2	Authors, affiliation, corresponding author	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Full names of all authors must be mentioned - Institutional affiliations, including that of the corresponding author, must be correctly and completely indicated. - the contribution of each author should be specified (where applicable) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To avoid confusion between first names and surnames, use capital letters for authors' surnames
3	Abstract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Well structured and concise -Clear, concise expression -Includes references to the issue addressed, essential elements of the research design, results achieved. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Be clear and specific! -Consider the abstract as an advertisement for your study! -Respect the imposed word limit!
4	Key words	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Must be closely related to the scientific content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Examine the keywords used in relevant articles from your field/

		-Must be precise, focused	topic or published in the journal where you intend to publish -Conduct online search using those keywords
5	Introduction	It should answer the following questions: -What is the problem? -Are there existing solutions? -Which solution is better? -What is its main limitation? -How do you hope to improve or contribute to it?	-Write the introduction with the “funnel model” in mind – from general to specific
6	Materials and methods	-Must include all important details enabling any reader to understand the experiment -All materials, instruments, devices, etc. used must be identified, described, presented	-Present appropriate control experiments. -Avoid adding comments and discussions. -Consider the use of supplementary materials: documents, spreadsheets, audio-video materials, etc.
7	Results	-Only important results should be presented -The presentation of results must be correlated with the experiment described in the Methods section -Results differing from previous publications or unexpected results should be highlighted - Statistical analysis results must be presented -Tables, figures, images are highly relevant	-Tell a clear and easy-to-understand story -Design tables and figures to contain synthesized information, with the text obligatory translated into the language of the article -Accompany each figure or image with an explanatory legend -Use colors within tables or figures only when necessary!
8	Discussion	-Explain how the results relate to the original question or objectives presented in the Introduction -Aims to interpret each presented result -Clarifies the extent to which the results are consistent with those reported by other researchers -Possible limitations are presented	-Avoid making claims that cannot be supported/ covered by the results presented -Do not introduce new ideas or terms
9	Conclusions	-Present what has been demonstrated in the paper and how the investigation contributes to the development of the field -Suggest possible future experiments/ research directions	-Do not summarize the paper! (the abstract has this role) -Avoid bold claims regarding the impact of the obtained results

10	References	-Correct citation of sources within the text - Texts taken verbatim must be placed between quotation marks - Consistency must exist between sources cited in the text and those listed in the final bibliography - The recommended/ accepted system must be used.	-Use primary sources whenever possible! - Prefer scientific publications rather than websites, brochures, accepted but not yet published articles; - Two citation styles may be used: author-focused (for important authors or a single cited study) or result-focused -Use representative and up-to-date scientific works.
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To the criteria and standards mentioned in Table 1, structured according to the sections of a study, we add other recommendations regarding the scientific style, footnotes, the drafting of tables and figures or the language of writing.

Scientific style

There are several styles in which a paper may be written, determined by several criteria: field/ specialization, type of paper, its purpose, its intentionality, intended audience, etc. According to Thomas and Turner (1994, apud Mack, 2018, p. 13), the style of a writing is defined according to five aspects or criteria:

- *Truth*: What is the writer's philosophical position on truth and how can it be known and communicated?
- *Presentation*: What does the writer (and the reader) value in the way of presentation?
- *Form of presentation*: What is the model for conveying the writer's thoughts to the reader?
- *Target audience*: Who is the intended reader? What does the writer assume about the reader?
- *Thought and language*: What is the relationship between the writer's thoughts and the language chosen to express them?

Footnotes are used to provide additional information and to emphasize an idea presented in the text. The information added must be relevant, genuinely useful for further explanation and reinforcement of an idea. Footnotes are particularly specific to the humanities and social sciences.

Tables and figures. We mention several recommendations regarding their use (after Repanovici, 2019, p. 44): Photographs, graphs, diagrams, papers, etc., intended to illustrate certain data and ideas from the content of the article, must be numbered in such a way as to allow reference within the text and must be accompanied by explanatory legends; it is recommended that the illustrations be numbered in a single sequence; tables must be properly numbered and titled; all illustrations and tables must be referred in the text. Their source may be cited in the legend.

Writing language – ideas must be expressed with clarity, objectivity, accuracy and conciseness.

The decision to publish a scientific study must be preceded by gathering important information regarding (adapted from Lövei, 2021, pp. 28-29): the publication calendar/ schedule (usually, information regarding the journal's publication frequency and publication dates is available on its website); updates regarding publication dates (special issues or thematic issues may appear, etc.); the time required from submission to publication (which may take several months); the publication standards imposed by the journal; circulation (regional, international journal, etc.); publication costs; the method of accessing the publication (open access or hybrid open access, etc.).

Lamanauskas (2019, p. 689) believes that writing a study should provide answers to three questions that the author must formulate: What do I know about this topic? What do I not know? Why did I conduct this research?

The dissemination of research results is highly important in the overall process of ensuring their visibility. Numerous studies (Schober, Farrington, Lacey, 2006; McGrath, 2016; Marín-González et al., 2017; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2020; Tudor, 2021) offer suggestions and recommendations for improving this process, which must take into account numerous criteria, related to the target group, the conditions of implementation (space, time), available resources, etc.

3. Research Methods

The investigation we conducted pursued several important **objectives**, presented below:

1. Identifying students' personal experience and level of academic writing competence.
2. Knowing students' opinion regarding the process of writing a scientific study.
3. Identifying the difficulties encountered by students in academic writing.
4. Analyzing participants' opinion regarding the importance of ethics in academic writing.

Research hypotheses and variables:

Hypothesis 1: *There is a positive association between a more adequate understanding of the academic writing process and the tendency of master's students to place greater value on the planning, revision and rigorous organization of scientific papers.*

The independent variable of the research is represented by the degree of understanding of the academic writing process, reflected by the identification of the characteristics, requirements and difficulties specific to academic writing (items 1, 4, 5, 7 and 20). **The dependent variables** concern the value attributed to the planning, revision and rigorous organization of scientific papers, highlighted by the importance given to drafting plans, text revision, the use of feedback and compliance with personal rules of academic writing (items 6, 8, 9 and 19).

Hypothesis 2: *Master's students who self-assess their academic writing competence at a higher level tend to be more responsible in using sources and in developing scientific papers.*

The independent variable of the research is represented by the self-assessed level of academic writing competence (item 3). **The dependent variables** concern responsible academic practices among master's students, reflected in the correct use and citation of bibliographic sources (items 10–13), verification of source credibility (item 14), as well as the understanding and acceptance of academic integrity standards and the concept of plagiarism (items 15, 16 and 18).

Description of the research instrument

The research method used was a questionnaire-based survey. The instrument applied to the subjects in the target group, through a Google form, was an opinion questionnaire, which included 20 items of different types, both with single and multiple responses, as well as scaled items. Through this instrument, we aimed to validate the established research hypotheses, as illustrated in the previous presentation of the research hypotheses and variables.

The sample consisted of 50 first-year master's students from the Faculty of Letters, enrolled in specializations belonging to the scientific fields of Humanities and Arts and Social Sciences. As graduates of a bachelor's degree program, the master's students have previous experience in developing scientific papers. However, the level of this experience varies depending on other non-formal or informal experiences they had acquired (example: participation in academic writing courses, student scientific events, projects that also had an academic writing component, etc.).

4. Results and Discussion

The results are presented according to the extent to which the subjects' responses contributed to the validation of the two research hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1: *There is a positive association between a more adequate understanding of the academic writing process and the master's students' tendency to place greater value on the planning, revision and rigorous organization of scientific papers.*

The first item of the questionnaire aimed to identify the master's students' opinions regarding the importance of academic writing skills for a future teacher. Over 90 % of the respondents stated that academic writing skills are highly relevant for a future teacher, while none of them considered these skills to be unimportant.

With regard to participation in previous academic writing courses, the responses were relatively evenly distributed across the three response options, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Participation in academic writing courses

What does academic writing mean to students? First of all, documentation and correct citation of sources, but also practicing argumentative skills. The complete results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Students' opinion on the requirements of academic writing

Regarding the qualities of a well-written academic text, students considered coherence, clear structure and clarity of expression to be the most important characteristics (figure 4).

Figure 4. Qualities of a well-written academic text

Producing a well-written academic text requires a writing plan. 80 % of the respondents expressed total agreement with this statement, while 14 % expressed partial agreement, and 6 % remained neutral.

Figure 5 presents the respondents' answers regarding the difficulty of writing a scientific paper according to its component sections.

Figure 5. Difficulties in conducting a scientific paper

When asked about the need to revise the text, 92 % of the respondents stated that this process should always be done and only 8 % answered sometimes.

To establish the final version, students primarily rely on teachers' observations, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Factors influencing the text revision process

In order to highlight a possible relationship between previous experience and a high level of academic writing competence and understanding of the academic writing process, two open-ended items were also included.

One of them asked students to mention 3 personal rules related to academic writing that they considered important and consistently followed, while the other requested them to identify the 3 most important difficulties they encountered in academic writing, in developing a scientific study.

Regarding personal rules, students frequently mentioned the following:

- **Clarity and coherence** – the logical and organized formulation of ideas and the use of clear, formal and accessible academic language.
- **Respect for sources and avoidance of plagiarism** – correct citation of sources, use of credible references and compliance with academic writing standards.
- **Rigorous documentation** – careful selection of bibliography and use of relevant, current and reliable sources.
- **Structuring the paper** – creating a clear writing plan, organizing chapters logically, and using headings for intuitive presentation.
- **Originality and personal contribution** – reformulating ideas in one's own words integrating personal interpretations and maintaining the authenticity of the work.
- **Revision and accuracy** – checking the grammar, spelling and textual coherence before submission.
- **Objectivity and argumentative rigour** – supporting statements with arguments and scientific sources, maintaining a neutral and academic tone.

The difficulties most frequently mentioned by respondents were:

- **Finding and selecting relevant sources** – identifying credible and up-to-date bibliography, as well as filtering useful information from a large volume of data.
- **Organizing and structuring ideas** – formulating a coherent logical thread, building the argument and writing in an appropriate academic structure.
- **Respecting academic style** – using formal and objective language, expressing ideas clearly and complying with citation and formatting standards.
- **Time management** – deadline pressure, insufficient time for documentation and writing.
- **Originality and formulation of personal contribution** – the balance between literature synthesis and personal input.
- **Synthesizing information** – integrating and summarizing sources effectively without losing essential ideas.
- **Methodology and interpretation of results** – selecting research methods and objectively interpreting data and conclusions.

In conclusion, the validation of hypothesis 1 is supported by the convergence of descriptive results obtained across several items of the questionnaire. Master's students who demonstrate an adequate understanding of the characteristics of academic writing highly value the planning and organization of the writing process. Thus, 80 % of respondents consider a writing plan necessary before drafting a scientific paper, while 92% believe that text revision should always be carried out. In addition, most students associate academic writing with documentation (86 %), correct citation of sources (86 %) and argumentation (80 %), while the main qualities of an academic text are considered to be coherence (94 %) and clear structure (90 %). The responses to the open-ended items confirm an orientation towards rigor, organization and systematic revision of scientific papers. Therefore, the results support the existence of a positive association between understanding the academic writing process and valuing rigorous practices for preparing scientific papers.

Hypothesis 2: *Master's students who self-assess their academic writing competences at a higher level tend to demonstrate more responsible academic practices in the use of sources and in the development of scientific papers.*

Although 40 % of respondents stated that they had never participated in an academic writing course, 72 % of them consider themselves to have a good level of development of academic writing skills. No student chose the extrem response options referring either to a very poor or an excellent level of development of the aforementioned competence.

An important aspect investigated, within the framework of quality academic writing, is the use of bibliographic sources. Students stated that they most frequently use e-books, websites, academic databases, but also printed texts. This last option is justified by the fact that many of the respondents study in the field of Humanities and Arts.

80 % of the students surveyed stated that they sometimes have difficulty identifying appropriate bibliographic sources, 8 % believe that this always happens, and 12 % stated that they never experience such difficulties.

More than half of the students' responses (52 %) indicate that they always use and cite bibliographic sources correctly, 32 % - sometimes, and 16 % - depending on the context. In contrast, the option "Never" did not register any responses (figure 7).

Figure 7. Correct use and citation of sources

In the same context, one of the questionnaire items asked students to mention to what extent deadline pressure can influence the correctness of source citation. 74 % of respondents declare that they always check the credibility of sources, while 22 % admit that they only do this sometimes, and 2 % stated that they never verify source credibility.

Regarding plagiarism sanctions, the responses were rather contradictory (see figure 8).

Figure 8. Students' opinion on the sanctioning of plagiarism

40 % of students expressed partial agreement with the idea that plagiarism should be severely punished and only 28 % expressed total agreement. Closely related to the concept of plagiarism, one of the items to which students responded asked them to assess the originality percentage of their semester projects. The responses are presented in figure 9.

Figure 9. Degree of originality of semester projects

For most students, plagiarism means taking over the argumentative structure of a work without mentioning the source, namely using fragments translated from a foreign work, without citing the original author (table 2).

Table. 2. Students' opinion on the meaning of plagiarism

No	Answer Option	%
a.	Integrating ideas from a source, reformulated in your own words, without indicating the author	60
b.	Taking over the argumentative structure of a paper without mentioning the source	82
c.	Using fragments translated from a foreign work, without citing the original author	82
d.	Reusing significant parts of your own previous works, without mentioning them	56
e.	Synthesizing several sources into an original text, citing all references used	8
f.	Using established definitions, marked with quotation marks and accompanied by a bibliographic reference	4

The obtained results support the partial to high validation of hypothesis 2.

To analyze the relationship between variables, the Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ) was used, as it is appropriate for ordinal variables and non-parametric distributions. The analysis aimed to identify associations between the self-assessed level of academic writing competence and various responsible academic practices, such as the correct use of sources, verification of source credibility, and perceptions regarding the originality of academic papers. The statistical significance threshold used was $p < 0.05$.

Thus, the validation of hypothesis no. 2 is supported by the existence of positive correlations between the self-assessed level of academic writing competence and several practices associated with academic responsibility. The most relevant statistical relationship was identified between self-assessed competence and the correct use of bibliographic sources ($\rho = 0.311$; $p = 0.028$). Positive relationships were also identified between the level of competence and the verification of the source credibility ($\rho = 0.268$; $p = 0.060$), as well as the perception regarding the originality of academic papers ($\rho = 0.298$; $p = 0.035$). These results suggest that master's students who perceive their academic competences at a higher level tend to adopt more responsible academic conduct in the use of sources and the development of scientific papers.

Therefore, hypothesis 2 can be considered confirmed, although the identified relationship is not completely uniform and suggests the need for additional training activities on ethics and academic integrity.

5. Conclusions

The research results highlight the fact that the investigated master's students display a relatively adequate understanding of the academic writing process and of the specific requirements involved in producing a scientific text. The majority of respondents associate academic writing with rigorous documentation, argumentation and the correct use of bibliographical sources, and the characteristics considered essential for an academic text are coherence, clarity and logical structure of ideas. At the same time, the students attach high importance to the planning and revision stages of the works, which indicates the value of an organized and reflective approach to **academic writing**.

The first hypothesis, regarding the existence of a positive association between understanding the academic writing process and valuing the rigorous planning, revision, and organization of scientific papers, was confirmed at descriptive and interpretive levels. The data obtained show that students who more clearly identify the demands and difficulties of academic writing tend to show a greater concern for structuring the text, using feedback, and revising content before the final form of the paper.

The second hypothesis highlighted the existence of positive relationships between the self-assessed level of academic writing competence and the adoption of responsible academic practices. Spearman correlation analysis indicated statistically significant associations between the level of competence and the correct use of bibliographic sources, as well as between academic competence and the perception of originality of works. Positive trends were also identified regarding the verification of the credibility of

sources and the concern for respecting the norms of academic integrity. These results suggest that the development of academic writing competences favors the assumption of more responsible and rigorous academic conduct.

At the same time, the research highlighted the existence of persistent difficulties in the academic writing process, especially in terms of selecting and synthesizing relevant sources, organizing ideas, and time management. These aspects indicate the need to strengthen the academic training of master's students through activities dedicated to research methodology, academic ethics, and the development of scientific writing skills.

Aknowldgment

This study is part of the research and training activity in the field of research, funded through the project “Cercetătorii viitorului /The researchers of the future”, project co-financed from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan- PNRR (Investiția10. Înființarea și susținerea financiară a unei rețele naționale de opt centre regionale de orientare în carieră ca parte a ERA TALENT PLATFORM – PNRR-III-C9-2022-I10).

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